

Errata to PhD thesis (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2613385>)

Note to Table 1: Only consequential errors have been listed.

Note to Table 2: The translations of `syn04types` proposals have been inserted automatically from my own translation. In a number of cases, however, this translation does not match the text syntax implied by the proposal, which may be confusing. For these cases, Table 2 provides the corrections. Usually this involves changes in interpunction and capitalization.

Table 1: general errors

page	text	correction
32, bullet 4	In <i>Cantos</i> ,	In <i>Cantos and Strophes in Biblical Hebrew Poetry</i> , a later elaboration of his dissertation,
45, bullet 1	... , that it, , that is, ...
101	notes 22-24	<i>replace by:</i> See the list of online materials on p. 306.
106, 3rd line from bottom	would have to be,	this would have to be,
163 n. 17	85 solutions	86 solutions; e.g. 1.3 (Lam 1,1b), 1.7 (Lam 1,2b), 2.2 (Lam 2,1b), 3.27 (Lam 3,13)
164 Ex. 8.6	צָרִים שְׁחָקוּ / עַל־מִשְׁבֹּתָהּ:	רְאוּהָ צָרִים שְׁחָקוּ / עַל־מִשְׁבֹּתָהּ:
126 lnr. 51	my liver	My liver (also p. 172 Ex. 8.15, corrected)
173 Ex. 8.16, proposed	בַּצֵּעַ אֶמְרָתוֹ . אֲשֶׁר צָוָה	(reverse indentation) בַּצֵּעַ אֶמְרָתוֹ אֲשֶׁר צָוָה .
178, other cases	1.6-73	1.6-7,
183, section 8.4, 2nd paragraph	would come up with.	would come up with, or by providing extra indications when the syntactic signals are weak.
209, last line	2.57-103	2.57.102
210, Ex. 9.8	... may be addressed	<i>delete</i>
213, l. 6 from bottom	and even as the subject	and not even as the subject
231, 10.3.2	However, as pointed out...	As pointed out...
240	Example 11.2	<i>delete entire example</i>
246, 3rd bullet		<i>duplicate point, delete</i>
288, last row	pPref	pRef (=participant reference)
295, l. 5 from bottom	ones hypotheses	one's hypotheses

Table 2: translations of syn04types proposals in the examples

Ex.	given translation	correction
8.9	that have been there from the days of old; (in the days) that her people fell into enemy hands	<i>duplicate translation; delete the first one.</i>
8.10	with no one to comfort her.	There was no one to comfort her.
8.11	looking for bread;	They are looking for bread.
8.14	and disowned his sanctuary.	He disowned his sanctuary.
8.15	my bowels churn.	my bowels churn,
8.16	(has done) what he decreed long ago:	what he decreed long ago.
8.17	he left me desolate.	He left me desolate,
8.18	he sated me with wormwood. ... trampled me in the dust.	He sated me with wormwood, and broke my teeth on gravel. He trampled me in the dust.
8.21	the little ones	The little ones
8.22	renew our days as of old;	Renew our days as of old,
8.23	and see my pain.	and see my pain:
8.24	[that] my bowels churn! My heart turns within me!	— my bowels churn, my heart turns within me—
8.26	Great is your faithfulness! “YHWH is my portion”,	“Great is your faithfulness! YHWH is my portion”,
8.30	but no one gives it to them. Those who once ate delicacies	but no one gives it to them, [to] the ones once eating delicacies.
8.31	sapphire their appearance. But now they are blacker than soot;	Sapphire is their appearance; they are blacker than soot.
8.32	<i>proposal not relevant to the example</i>	<i>delete</i>
8.33	<i>proposal not relevant to the example</i>	<i>delete</i>
8.35	her young women grieve. And as for herself:	her young women grieve, and as for herself:
8.37	the little ones ask for bread,	The little ones ask for bread,
8.38	has destroyed his strongholds. And he multiplied ...	has destroyed his strongholds, and multiplied ...
8.39	and did not remember ...	And he did not remember ...
9.3	I call your name,	I called your name,
9.6	now cling to garbage heaps. The punishment of ...	now cling to garbage heaps, and the punishment of ...